

SOCIAL WORK PATTERNS IN NIGERIA: STRATEGIES FOR RURAL COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper is about the examination of the patterns of social work in Nigeria and how they affect rural community development in Akwa Ibom State. To get over this research goal, three (3) objectives and three (3) research questions were raised to guide the review of related literature for the study. However, secondary data were gathered to address the research questions via journals, newspapers, policy frame work, and evaluation reports of projects and programmes carried out. Findings revealed that social work patterns include social case work, social group work, and community organization. The summation of which is to bring changes or improvements into the rural community for a higher standard of living of the residents. Based on the findings, study recommended among others that deliberate effort should be made by stake holders to adopt social work patterns in giving attention to the needs of rural community dwellers in Akwa Ibom State.

KEYWORDS: Social work; Community Organization, Community Development; Strategies; Akwa Ibom State

INTRODUCTION

Social work is an art, a science, a profession that helps people to solve personal, group, and community problems (Smith 2006 in Umoren, 2015). Social work can also be viewed as a profession aims at promoting social change, problem-solving in human relationships, as well as empowerment of people to live a qualitative life-style. Beyond this, Okolo (2002) argued strongly that, social work is a helping institution which exists primarily for the purpose of assisting society and its members to tackle or address day to day problems as they occur. For instance, social workers must ensure that individuals, families, groups, and even communities have their problems prevented or resolved to avoid any unforeseen or associated danger (Ekong, 2010).

In the light of the above, social workers could use their technical, scientific, and relational ability or expertise to identify certain deficiency in emotional, economic, social or health issues and provide remedies that could put them back in the original state. In society currently, Umoren (2015) noted that, there are many people of varied characteristics. These

include the aged, children, the sick, the poor, the physically and mentally challenged, destitute, delinquents and other forms of dehumanizing conditions. The social work institution, functions as helping agency, not only to ensure that, the problems of community members are prevented or resolved, but also to equip the affected individual or restore the social functioning of such individuals.

Social functioning, scholars (Okolo, 2002; Farley and Smith, 2006) noted, is the usefulness of different aspects of the lives of individuals in relation to their daily interactions, and relationships within the environment, transcending both human and materials. It is worthy of note that, an individual or group may be overwhelmed with personal or and social or structural problems to the extent that, when the problems are even solved, it is still difficult for such an individual or group to function well in the society. This experience becomes the obvious reason why the social worker must go beyond merely providing solutions to the problems. It is also ethical and moral for the social worker, to ensure that practical steps are taken to both restore as well as facilitate the functional abilities of those involved, either in personal or aided capacity. For instance, the general welfare of the older adults of 60+ can be enhanced or achieved as solution to their impoverished condition. But that does not translate in any way to the well-being of those with hearing and sight impairment, arthritis pains, hypertension, kidney problems etc. which result in limitations in Activities of Daily Living (ADLs) or Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADLs) (Offong, 2020).

The social worker therefore, is expected to bring to bear specialized skills and technical knowledge for the amelioration of challenge or health issues and lift the affected person(s) from social malfunctioning to the status of social functionality. However, social work profession or practice revolves round three basic processes of casework, group work, and community organization which by extension could lead to more effective societal well-being and development. The major goal of which is believed to create social welfare in both rural and urban communities. Social welfare involves those non-profit functions of the society (public or private) which are clearly aimed at alleviating unpleasant conditions of the casualties or vulnerable persons in society. In other words, social welfare is an interventional measure intended to enhance or maintain the social functioning of human beings through education, health services, housing, income maintenance, and personal welfare (Ekong, 2010).

In line with this background, activities of social workers are capable of dovetailing into a more rewarding community development. Development in this context would mean, improving situations in individual and society through constructive planning, social investment, awareness in social responsibility, potentials and new capacities' engagements, and growth toward a more matured and responsible social actors (Ekong, 2010; Offong, 2023). Emerging from this strength therefore, it is believed that social inquiry on the patterns of social work in Nigeria in general, would reveal better options for effective rural social welfare and development in Akwa Ibom State in particular. The main objective of this paper was to establish how social work patterns in Nigeria can be used as strategies for effective development in Akwa Ibom State.

METHODOLOGY

The paper was written in relation to the current realities of social work patterns in Nigeria and how this could promote community development in Akwa Ibom State. The state is one of the 36 states structure in Nigeria, created from the former Cross River State in 1987. However, Akwa Ibom State is operating with 31 Local Government Areas. These Local Government areas have more of rural features than urban characteristics, Thus, the challenge of rural community development is pronounced. Adopting models or patterns of social work in Nigeria as strategies to facilitate rural community development question is obvious and rewarding task.

Methods and materials for the study would entails literature review methodology, where secondary data sources, which include text books, journals, magazines, newspapers, unpublished monographs, evaluation reports from NGOs related to case management were gathered and used to discuss variables that were relevant to the subject matter of the paper. These variables were-social works patterns (SWPs), Relationship of SWPs to Community Development, and the critique of these patterns in community development in Akwa Ibom State.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Social Work Patterns

Scientifically or conventionally, social work is characterized by three concerns in its methodological drive as described below:

Social Case Work

This approach is to involve a close face to face relationship, mainly on person to person basis. In other words, “social case workers” attend to those individuals who are unable to achieve a fairly normal adjustment to life, because of their current miserable status or vulnerability, which require outside help or attention (Umoren, 2018). In line with this notion, casework is carried out on individual basis reflecting a person-centred model and in situation where the privacy or the confidentiality is a necessity to deal with individual problems. For example, information gathering, involves obtaining consent (permission), maintaining confidentiality about the person involves in case management (Ezeh and Mba, 2004).

Equally, Campton and Galaway (1999) argued that in case work, especially patients or client in the hospice, drug rehabilitation centre, women's shelter or terminally inclined patients in the hospital, service agreement is of essence. For instance:

- (i) Negotiations between the case manager and the clients are the necessary requirements;
- (ii) Clear definition of the problems of the clients must be carried out;
- (iii) Mutually agreeable solution must be identified;
- (iv) Action plan and implementation become the hallmark using community resources, monitor and also evaluate the outcomes;

The above conditions reflect the realities of covenant model where “gift” aspect of professional identity and undistorted or the unbound commitment of social worker to the individual needs, are parts of the template (Miller, 1999 in Umoren, 2015). Social case work in this context has two targets of which are:

- (i) That of helping the vulnerable person or an individual with a known difficult situation in playing expected roles in his live and living (clinical social case work); and
- (ii) Those aspects of social institutions that fail to support vulnerable individuals fulfilling role expectations are to be motivated.

Social Group Work

Group work is a method in social work which utilizes the group as the tool with which to effect the desired changes in the social functioning of troubled persons. Umoren (2015) noted that social group work is unique in functioning style. This is because, it has improvement capacity for the group members. This capacity according to Umoren connotes undistorted ability for a mature relationship, self-awareness, and a greater sense of belonging. Ezeh and Mbah (2004) had observed earlier on that, in the colonial era, Group Work services were provided through boy's club, women's welfare clubs, community youth councils and community centres.

Currently, efforts by non-governmental or governmental agents or agencies have changed the paradigm by adopting and using youth groups, women associations, community elders' or leaders' forum, fathers' of faith, Christian movements, political groups etc. as major domains for the administration of social welfare services. More specifically, the social worker often engages in supportive services for the existing groups by starting with clarification, suggestion, development of alternative solutions, and reflection. These are considered in the words of Umoren (2015) as social workers through groups engagement. For instance, still Umoren noted:

- (i) Impending social problems emerge from or is identified with individual during group sessions;
- (ii) Social group worker would utilize the group as a tool to bring about desired changes in social functioning of the troubled persons;
- (iii) Social group worker would collaborate with community organization in laying emphasis on the situational context of behavioural change, before the provision of services;
- (iv) Social group worker would involve small group interactions as mechanism to facilitate social change. For instance, Umoren (2015) observed that, drug and alcohol addicts, unemployed school leavers, juvenile offenders, criminals, people with physical and mental disabilities, older adults with impairment or disabilities, etc. are among many groups that call for social work intervention.

Scholars (Skidmore and Thackeray, 1982 in Okolo, 2002) argued that social group work (SGW) provide the basis to believe that, working with two or more people enhance social group functioning and also achieve socially desirable improvement in an individual. Again, Friedlander and Apte (1980) cited in Okolo (2002) noted that, to effectively achieve the goal of group functioning and individual social functioning, social group worker employ one of the following strategies:

- (i) Authoritarian Strategy: in this strategy the SGW simply issue order or directive for the group members to obey;

- (ii) **Personification Strategy:** it is seen here that, the social group worker (SGW) becomes a model for the members of his client group to imitate as they interact with one another;
- (iii) **Perceptive Strategy:** this strategy requires the group members to perform their activities according to the instructions of the social worker who never bother to assist members of the group in discovering their talents or abilities;
- (iv) **Manipulative Strategy:** in this strategy, the SGW predetermines certain decisions and guides the group to arrive at such decisions, pretending as if the group took the decision; and
- (v) **Enabling Strategy:** this strategy defines the task of SGW primarily in terms of assisting the group members to be fully involved in the activities of the group, as well as develop and utilize their own skills and abilities.

Friedlander and Apte in Okolo (2002) still noted that, the knowledge and intervention skills employed in working with groups are basically same with those used in working with individuals. Group dynamics is essential in bringing about distinction between group work and individual. The effectiveness of social work intervention for the group, and individual that constitute the group depends on the knowledge or group dynamics which is the interaction and forces within small face- to – face groups.

Community Organization

Community organization is seen as a process by which a community identifies its needs or objectives, gives priority to them, develops the “confidence” and “will” to work at them, finds resources (internal and External) to deal with them and in doing so, extends and develops cooperative and collaborative attitudes and practices in the community (Ross, 1967 in Ekong, 2010). In this definition, the word “process” connotes a movement from identification of a problem to solution of the problem or attainment of the objective in the community. Beyond this, community organization process is the capacity of the community to function as an integrated unit that grows as it deals with one or more community problems. The task of a professional worker in community organization is to help initiate, nourish, and develop this process. More than this, the task is also to make this process conscious, deliberate, and understandable (Ekong, 2010). This explains why Okolo (2002) and Ottong and Basse (2009) had observed that community organization is one of the primary methods of social work as it deals with intervention in the community to solve varied problems through collection involvement. Against this background, Siddiqui (1997) has identified eight principles of community organization. These include;

- The principle of specific objectives;
- The principle of planning;
- The principle of peoples participation;
- The principle of intergroup approach;
- The principle of democratic functioning;
- The principle of flexible organization;
- The principle of optimum utilization of indigenous resources; and
- The principle of cultural orientation

In the light of those principles, effective community organization can be understood in the following ways:

- i. It is a mean and not an end: In this sense, it is the method or a means to enable people to live a happy and fully developed life. It refers to a method of intervention whereby a community consisting of individuals, group, or organizations are helped to engage in planned and collective action in order to provide their needs and deal with their problems.
- ii. Community organization has the potency to promote community solidarity and the practice of democracy: Thus, community organization is a measure of discouraging segregation, discrimination, exclusion and disruptive influences which could threaten the wellbeing of the community and the functioning of social institutions.
- iii. Identification of the community: The designated community is the client of the community organization worker. Therefore, such community must be clearly identified. As soon as the community is identified, the community organizer would show concern, even for other related communities. This is because, no community is expected by the rules of the game to be isolated from the programme, as well as the use of the local resources for the good of all.
- iv. Fact-finding and needs Assessment: Community organization programmes are believed to be fused with the community elements. Siddqui (1997) noted that proper fact finding and assessment of the community needs are the prerequisites for starting programme in any community of choice. Offong (2023) noted that, it is an acceptable standard for local community services to be indigenous, grass root oriented, rather than to be imposed from the outside. In other word, community organization must revolve around the felt needs of the community or substantial number of persons in the community (outbreak of disease, dilapidated road, energy disconnection, attacks by bandits etc).
- v. Mobilization and utilization of the available resources in the community: This implies that existing social welfare resources in the community such as health centre, POS, market, church, school, town hall, shopping mall, government, non-governmental organizations, faith based organizations, community associations, etc. In addition to these resources, indigenous human resource must be put to optimum use (mass mobilization and participation).
- vi. Participatory Planning: It is of essence that, the community organization worker must accept the need for participatory planning through the pre-prepared blue-print in the beginning of what he or she intends to do with the community (taking into consideration the needs of the community, available and accessible resources, agency objectives and capability). Planning in this context involves cycle of implementation, evaluation, adjustment and sustainability.
- vii. Voluntary cooperation: Community organization is based on mutual understanding, agreement and voluntary acceptance. It must eschew the non-coercion, non-compulsion regime. It should be a reflection of democratic principles (majority carry the day), harmonious relationship, (a demonstration of “united we stand, divided we fall axiom”), non-regimentation, non-imposition from outside, but derivable from the inner freedom, and free will that unite those who engage or practice it.

- viii. Development of the spirit of cooperation rather than competition: Community organization entails the intensification of the spirit of cooperation (where everyone comes together for a common goal, being that of solving commonly identified problems) rather than competition among groups, agencies, community associations, and communities.
- ix. Involvement of indigenous leadership: Community organization is structured to identify and work with local leaders (formal and informal) who are accepted and command influence among major and sub-groups in the community. This has, in several instances become major steps in community integration and organization. These leaders could be traditional, governmental, non-governmental, opinion based, Faith Based etc.
- x. Limited use of authority or compulsion: It could be necessary and useful to apply authority and compulsion any way in getting things work in the interest of the community and institution. This is to be applied persuasively, as little as possible, for a short period and as a last resort. In doing so, people will learn together, acquire skills together and develop the spirit of cooperation.
- xi. Flexibility in programmes and services: This requirement is basic in a result-oriented community organization. Therefore, social welfare agencies and need-related programmes must be responsive enough to adjust due to changing conditions, problems, and needs of community life. As we all know, community is part of the changing or dynamic world, which suggest that, inevitably, it is also affected by change phenomenon. Consequently, needs and problems are constantly changing, it is necessary that programmes and services are flexible enough to meet periodic changes.
- xii. Continued Evaluation Participation: In the development of programmes to meet community needs (rural or urban or both), there must be inbuilt evaluation, stock-taking, feedback process to see how effective and penetrating, the action has been and what has been achieved with the given level of inputs. This will enhance the replication of the blue-prints and practices elsewhere.

In the modern world, effective and result-oriented community organization must be based on certain skills that drive proficiency and competence. These skills include what Ottong and Basse (2009) identified as skills in:

- (i) Rapport Establishment;
- (ii) Identification of Needs and Analysis;
- (iii) Resources Mobilization (manpower, money, material, time etc.);
- (iv) Programme Planning;
- (v) Programme Management (high or low performance);
- (vi) Evaluation (talk or feedback; assessment; research);
- (vii) Recording;
- (viii) Encouraging Community Participation;
- (ix) Working with the Group;
- (x) The Interest of individuals; and
- (xi) Mobilizing community Action.

Community organization happens in variety of contexts that define community itself (Ottong and Basse 2009; Ekong 2010; Umoren, 2015). For instance, community in the

word of Mencil (1944) in Umoren (2015) refers to two major grouping of people:

- All the people in a geographic area – a village, a town, a city, a neighbourhood, or a district in a city, a province, or a state, a nation or in the world; and
- Groups of people who share some common interest or function, such as welfare, agriculture, education, religion, place of work etc.

In this context, community organization is involved to bring these persons together to develop some awareness of, and feeling for their “community” and to work at common problems arising out of the interest they have in common or shared. It can further be broken down thus:

- (I) Shared place – people are seen coming together and share a common geographic place such as local village, community, local government, state, region, city or town. For instance, local residents may come together to address neighbourhood concern (safety, housing, or basic services). Therefore, problem solving through Community – Based Organizations (CBOs), Neighbourhood Associations, and Tenants Organizations are common forms of shared – place practice (Anam, 2014).
- (II) Shared work situation – community organizing efforts is also carried out among people who share a work situation or workplace. For instance, farm laborers, industrial workers in factories who may be in camp or quarters. These people could be brought together in consciousness of their working conditions, job security, wages, and benefits. Social or community organizing workers may bring to bear CO steps to put them in the right perspective to tackle existing problems.
- (III) Shared Experiences and Concerns – organizing usually occurs among people who have concerns about the same issues. These include abused children, drug abusers, discrimination that holds people back for achieving goals; equally those who are physically challenged (cripples, visual impairments, hearing impairments, aged with known disabilities etc) could come together to create conditions for independent living.

In view of the above background, community organization (CO) can only thrive in contexts. The study has identified such contexts to include, shared place; shared work situation or work place; and shared experiences and concerns. In these contexts community organizers/workers would employ certain steps to achieve expected goals – They include:

- (I) Consciousness of needs;
- (II) Spreading the consciousness of needs;
- (III) Projection of consciousness of needs;
- (IV) Emotional impulse to meet the need quickly;
- (V) Core group formation (CBOs) in readiness for solution;
- (VI) Group work and Group meeting to discuss modalities and alternatives process;
- (VII) Identification of problems, investigation and analysis;
- (VIII) Role playing; Mobilization for Action;
- (IX) Integration of option; and
- (X) Evaluation – talk back, feedback and reflection.

The task of the professional worker in community organization as earlier mentioned is to help initiate, nourish, and develop this process consciously or deliberately for improvement in the assigned or community of interest.

PATTERNS OF SOCIAL WORK AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN AKWA IBOM STATE

The term community is derived from the Latin word “Communis” meaning “common” (Ndukwe, 2005; Ekong, 2010). Community therefore, is a group of people living together as a group of social unit within a larger one with a common interest (Olewe 2001 in Umoren, 2015). Beyond this, it can also be viewed as a group of people living within a specific geographical area (shared place; shared work situation; shared experiences and concerns; a village; a city, a nation etc). In a nutshell, community is seen as a solidarity institution where primary interaction is experienced. Solidarity institutions in this context, refers to institutions whose functions are to operate through solidarity (family, ethnic groups, voluntary organization, and residential groups). Often time, several communities had always viewed social work force as intruders, agents of government who have the money to share, tarred their roads, pay school fees and hospital bills of the sick and many more expectations. Consequently, community youth could unleash mayhem, seize their belongings or drive them out of the community despite strict adherence to the requirements for community entry.

Social work essentially involves “Social Case Work”, otherwise known as “a person-centred model” in a given community. This model practically is carried out on individualized situation. In other word, the main target is to help individuals who are limited or having difficulty in performing role expectations. This explains why it is also called micro-practice or clinical-social work for such individual as (drug addict, alcoholic abuser, traumatized unemployed person, older adult with disabilities, juvenile offender, mentally deranged person). Individually and collectively, they exist in communities. Therefore, solving each person's limitation or challenge would result in solving the community's challenge. This is because, the social worker is a professional agent with the capacity to handle ailing health or social situations, possessing as well the power of referral to appropriate service providers (aided community development). Yet the expectations of community are more than what the workers could carry. Often community would expect social workers to be miracle workers.

Scholars (Nyerere 1978, in Ndukwe, 2005; Ekong, 2010) noted that community development is summed up as man's capacity to expand his own consciousness, create enabling power over himself, environment and his society. This is true, but must be surrender to government according to community reasoning. Nyerere stressed that “man” is the central pivot around which development revolves. In this regard, development can be seen as progress made for man by man and of man. This means that, man is not only the recipient or beneficiary of development efforts, but must also initiate the effort to develop himself. Man must show the desire to develop before development can come. Exceptional development effort is the one which leads to expansion and growth of man's inner qualities on one hand, and raise man's ability to dominate himself, become less dependent and more proficient in his functionality. Social case work or clinic-social work, remains the mitigating or driving force to fix man in every development process and also in his cultural setting, being mindful of his privacy.

The second social work pattern is Social Group Work (SGW). This strategy utilizes such group as unemployed school leavers, criminals, people with physical and mental disabilities, frail older adults, juvenile delinquents, drug addicts, alcohol abusers etc as the tools with which to effect the desired changes in their social functioning in a given community or socio-cultural context (Umoren, 2015). The social Group worker would draw up the under-

listed processes to achieve his or her goal of intervention:

- i. Outreach and identification;
- ii. Engagement and communication;
- iii. Assessment of problems and strengths or resources;
- iv. Develop care plan which involves networking; and identifying other resources to address needs;
- v. Provision of support services or referral;
- vi. Advocate for the needy and follow-up.

Interaction of SGW intervention with the community in the word of Raynor et al (1983) in Ndukwe (2005) are multidimensional. For instance.

i. Community Development (CD) is a process whereby local groups are assisted to clarify and express their needs, objectives, take collective action to meet those needs. At the center of this assistance is always Social Group Worker/agency. Hence, the affected person must cooperate with the Social Group Worker.

ii. CD is the effort of the local community to utilize local resources (natural-land, stream, forest etc; social-health service; schools; market; good road network; faith based resources; governmental resources-employment opportunity etc); at the centre of it must be the social group worker/agency. However, he must not do this in isolation with the community supports.

iii. In order to facilitate community development process, there must be a professional community development worker (PCDW). The PCDW is a person who is always on the move to achieve (goal-gether), organize, sensitize, mobilize, and coordinate the efforts of other people into the development process (Ottong and Bassey 2009). This must be allowable and supported by every strand of person to get the desired results.

iv. The PCDW receives specific training in community social work and general social services. On the strength of this, there is a strong relationship between social group work and community development. This explains why successful implementation or execution of Community Development Projects depends on the qualifications and qualities of the community development worker (CDW) or Social Group Worker (SGW) and the cooperative attitude of the community.

However, there are 4 important roles of social group worker (SGW) or community development worker (CDW). Ottong and Bassey (2009) identified them as;

- ❖ The Guide: as a guide, CDW helps the community to determine and locate the means and resources of achieving the development goals of the community. He directs the strategies of achieving development;
- ❖ The Helper: As a helper the CDW makes the process of development easier than it is supposed to be. He encourages cooperation among members of the community. In terms of the group dynamics, CDW must ensure good inter-relation between and among groups in the community. He breaks down (ice breaking) the technical aspect of community project to the understanding and appreciation of the community members who are ready to support the process.
- ❖ An Expert: As an expert, the CDW has a special knowledge of the field. He is skilled in the general art and science of general social work, community development, and social welfare services. He (CDW) provides data to aid in crucial decision making. As an expert, he carried out researches, diagnosis, planning and evaluation, education, and provides technical information and advise on methods and strategies.

- ❖ The Social Physician: As a physician, CDW carries out diagnosis and treatment of the community. He considers the history and internal or group dynamics within the community; where the community can volunteer useful information.
- ❖ CDW identifies the problems of the community and prescribes projects and programmes that may provide solution to the problems. This can only work when the community members agree with the direction provided.

Moreover, the Community Development Worker (CDW) cannot get a better results from any of these roles if he or she does not engage in the performance of these specific functions (Ekong, 2010; Umoren, 2015):

- i. Identification of community problems and needs;
- ii. Identification of the strategies to address the needs;
- iii. Panning, Evaluation and monitoring of project and programme;
- iv. Identification the leadership structure and coordination of project and programme implementation.
- v. Helping in revenue generation, budgeting, and management of funds;
- vi. Creation of awareness and public enlightenment of community programmes and projects;
- vii. Conflict resolution template and enforcement;
- viii. Linking the community with other agencies, government, and organizations for external assistance;
- ix. In Africa in general and Nigeria in particular, social group worker who may also act as community development worker (CDW) assist in the rehabilitation, and caring for the indigent children, orphans, widows, widowers, elderly, and disable persons (Umoren, 2015).

Ekong (2010) stressed that community must be organized before orderly development can take place. Ekong still noted that, the practice of organizing the community consists of interventions that enhance, sustain or sever existing linkages units. Thus, the geographical community is no more a self-sufficient unit, but rather a unit which depends largely on other community of interests in order to attain its own objectives or meet its own felt needs. Community organization therefore, “is a process by which a community is mobilized to identify its needs or recognize a problem within its environment, develop the will to work together in meeting such needs or resolving the problem, find resources internally and or externally to deal with the problems or needs, take action in respect to them and in so doing develop cooperative and collaborative attitudes and practices in the community” (Ekong, 2010). In the light of the above, community organization is driven by the following objectives:

- Members of the community to obtain a consciousness of belonging to a community and sharing common problems and finding common solutions.
- Community organization as a social work pattern is to bring the residents of a community (urban or rural) together for the purpose of meeting certain needs.
- To achieve a more effective socialization by community stamping or personality on individual and build into that individual a feeling, emotion, interest and concern for the community.
- To attain social control directed towards the development of loyalty and commitment for unity of action and attainment of community goal.

- To achieve the coordination of groups and their activities for the attainment of specific common goal.
- To prevent the introduction of undesirable influences or conditions into the community.
- To develop local leadership to direct local activities by calling for participation and concentrations voluntarily for social welfare, projects and programmes.
- To centralize local efforts to avoid unnecessary duplications.

The above objectives are achievable through four major models in Akwa Ibom State.\

- (i) Locality Development Model
 - Problem – Solving – Structures,
 - Community's power base to stimulate voluntary participation,
 - Strengthening of local leadership to manage resources,
 - Information sharing mechanism to encourage interest.
- (ii) The Social Planning Model uses research, information and analysis to address emerging social challenges in a community – child trafficking, ritual killings, kidnapping, environmental health problem. In this case, task force, professionals etc can be engaged to bring up solutions.
- (iii) Social Action Model – this involves effort to increase the power and resources of low income or relatively powerless or marginalized people – advocacy, strike, match, etc to attract the attention of those in powers.
- (iv) Community partnership/coalitions model – this strategy combined elements of the above three strategies. That is, locality development, social planning, and social actions are integrated or form coalitions to attend to such social challenges as – drug addiction, prostitution, cultism, health challenges, school drop-out, food, etc. the coalition would design specific programmes, policies and practices at the village, ward, local government, state, federal and senatorial constituencies.

It is obviously revealed that social work patterns (social case work, social group work and social organization) are the promoters of community development in general and Akwa Ibom State in particular. This is because the Social Case Worker (SCW), Social Group Worker (SGW)/Community Development Worker (CDW) and Community Organization Worker (COW) function interchangeably, concertedly, collaboratively to achieve improvement of the quality of life for the community residents if adopted and utilized in Akwa Ibom State.

CRITIQUE OF SOCIAL WORK PATTERNS AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN AKWA IBOM STATE.

There is a pact between the individual and corporate Society. This implies that, individual is expected as a responsible citizen to contribute his or her quota towards the common good, such as respect for laid-down regulation and moral obligation for mutual and peaceful existence (Ezeh and Mbah, 2004). While the corporate society owes the individual every support, avenue, and enabling environment to succeed and improve a living. However, this interactive social environment between the individual and the society are usually disrupted and fraught with inadequacies. Modo (2015) noted that there are discrepancies culturally, sexually, socially (where one is sick, healthy, poor, rich, lack opportunity or enablement to compete etc.). On the strength of this, Modo stressed that social welfare

services were created and social work strategies adopted.

Government at all levels had worked out modality to spread welfare services to the eligible in every community using accredited agencies such as Ministry of Women Development and Social Welfare in Akwa Ibom State with various departments. It is not to discredit or spite anybody to say that, many government and non-governmental agencies are not living up to expectations. Many Welfare packages often found it way to individual homes to the exclusion of vital target (VT). Whereas international organizations have spelt out exclusive rights and all inclusive mechanism for the vulnerable and incapacitated. Ezeh and Mbah (2004) noted that social work and its patterns (social case work, social Group Work, and community organization) are all laudable strategies to address needs of the vulnerable groups, from individual – Group – and community, yet there are many untouched challenges because of social exclusivity and nepotism. Volunteers, even paid workers in social work may decide to be self-centred or selective due to the directive of the welfare/service organizations.

This of course, becomes impediment, or the affected individual, group, or community may refuse to cooperate, equally, this is a force of truncation. The challenge before us is how to engage the stakeholders effectively in the process (Ottong and Basse, 2009; Anam, 2014). Anam (2014) on his own identified the following as stakeholders – individual, family, community, government, Faith Based organizations (FBOs), Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs). These groups may fine-tune the “modus operandi”, and make the social workers and clients to foster a sense of purpose (Ekong, 2010).

MAJOR FINDINGS

- i. Social work is a professionally oriented effort in getting community residents on toes to address common problems.
- ii. Social work has three (3) patterns or strategies to achieve its objectives. These are – Social Case Work (clinical social case work or human centered); Social Group Work (small group interactions); Community Organization (empowering people for their development).
- iii. Community residents in Akwa Ibom State are made up of varied characteristics which include the healthy, the aged, children (male and female), the destitute, delinquents, orphans, widows, widowers, etc. all of them co-exist within the communal social ecology in Akwa Ibom State.
- iv. The social work institution whenever, made relevance functions as helping agency, not only to ensure that, the problems of community members are prevented or resolved, but also equip the affected individual or restore the social functioning of such individuals. (This is a plus for the community).
- v. Social workers are always prompt, focused, with goal getter spirit, mobilizer, preachers, directors, counsellors, advocates, referral agents (who doesn't take chances), consistent in the elimination of human miseries (penuries), promoters of human welfare and improved quality of lives.
- vi. Social workers and service organizations were found to sometime adopt idiosyncratic approach where the intents of their heart are super imposed on the interest of the community or the agencies, or the interests of the agencies are superior to that of the

community.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

Social work pattern or strategies do not de-emphasise local initiative, top-bottom, self-help in community development, but aided self-help where experts are in collaboration, coalition and in partnership with the community members (indigenes and non-indigenes). Beyond this, social work patterns adopt problem-specific-solution-approach whether of individual, family, community and statewide manner. Therefore, it is more result oriented, quick response, target oriented and evident based. If adopted and utilized, there will be a paradigm shift from the conventionalized, rigid and age long method. Consequently, social work should be promoted as a professional discipline in institutions of learning, graduates employed in the ministry of women and social welfare in Akwa Ibom State or used as volunteers. Stakeholders must come to terms with the realities of the phenomenal change, with regards to community development. Again, the progress expected from social work through various strategies can only be achieved if the principle of selflessness is promoted and substituted for greed, self-centeredness, corrupt practices and nepotism.

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